

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF THE MAGEC SPINAL ROD UNDER COMPRESSIVE AND SHEAR LOADING CONDITIONS

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Advancements in spinal surgery have led to the development of innovative implant systems, such as the MAGEC (Magnetic Expansion Control) spinal rod, which offers dynamic deformity correction in patients of EOS (Early-onset scoliosis). To assess the mechanical behaviour of this groundbreaking technology, finite element analysis (FEA) is employed to simulate the response of the MAGEC spinal rod when subjected to compressive and shear loading conditions. This study unveils insights into structural integrity, stress distribution, and deformation patterns, aiding in optimising design and informing clinical decisions for improved patient outcomes in spinal deformity correction.

Keywords: Spinal Implant, MAGEC, Finite Element Analysis, Early-onset Scoliosis (EOS)

INTRODUCTION

Scoliosis is a skeletal deformation disease which causes the spine to curve, creating severe discomfort and challenging everyday lives (Hresko [1]). Early-onset scoliosis (EOS) is a medical deformity which has been present for decades affecting approximately 2% of children and teenagers worldwide, and in severe instances can result in complete immobility and potential fatalities ([1], Ágústsson et al. [2]). EOS is comprised of a myriad of conditions, which can be developed from congenital malformations, neuromuscular conditions, and inherited bone dysplasia and syndrome states (Karol [3]). The history of EOS medical treatment began with non-surgical practices including casting/bracing, attempting to prevent the progression of skeletal deformation and preserve cardiac functions (Teoh et al. [4]). The term infantile idiopathic scoliosis was coined by Harrenstein in 1936, while conducting studies entailing forty-six EOS cases. Harrenstein reported that the disease was related to the skeletal disorder rickets and responded well to casting techniques. Though, overtime this treatment unveiled limitations as the technique was impractical due to the moulded cast resulting in immobility of the patient (Dede and Sturm [5]). Interest to resolve the issue of tackling patient skeletal development whilst treating diagnosis of EOS has grown over recent years (Anari et al. [6]). Fletcher and Bruce [7] detail how EOS continues to present a formidable obstacle for physicians, praising growing spine techniques such as the Vertical Expandable Prosthetic Titanium Rib (VEPTR) device for improving spinal angle. However, this technique adds the requirement of additional surgical adjustment and carries high-risk complications. Bess et al. [8] analysed issues concerning 910 growing surgeries and identified the risk complications per surgery to be roughly 20%. These findings suggested that treatment difficulties could be resolved by eliminating the requirement of further surgical intervention to lengthen the spinal rod as the patient's body develops.

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Spinal neurosurgery saw a significant technological advancement in this area when the MAGEC (Magnetic Expansion Control) growing rod was introduced across Europe in 2009 (Jenks et al [9]). This cost-effective treatment attempts to correct the angle of the spine as the skeleton continues to grow and mature. MAGEC technology avoids additional surgery to replace rods that accompany the growth of adolescents diagnosed with the disease, which traditional treatments required (Hickey et al. [10]). Current research illustrates the positive results achieved by MAGEC technology. Heydar et al. [11] discusses an experimental study examining 18 patients suffering from scoliosis. This study's results show an average spinal deformation angle improvement of 48%, and this is a common pattern found within most published literature on this subject. Dannawi et al. [12] also provides improved results from alternative analysis which achieved an overall spinal angle improvement of 32%. However, these studies fail to discuss the burden of design complications which have been discovered overtime after surgery has commenced. Up to 38% of MAGEC device failures have been reported after implantation from mechanical wear and overbearing forces applied from the human body (Joyce et al. [13]) (Fig 1a-b). The MAGEC device has been analysed by means of retrieval observation studies with various components displaying evidence of fractures and structural wear [13].

FIGURE 1 (a-b) MAGEC growing rod failures. Reproduced with permissions from [13]

One frequently failing component which is highlighted throughout current literature is the radial bearing. Joyce et al. [13] performed a UK retrieval analysis study examining 34 explanted MAGEC devices, with 74% demonstrating substantial damage to the radial bearing. Figure 2a illustrates a failed radial bearing from Joyce's study with the inner cage detaching from exterior ring of the component, and an excessive buildup of debris. Similarly, Panagiotopoulou et al. [14] carried out radiographs of nine retrieved implants, assessing them macroscopically and microscopically for material loss, with the radial bearing demonstrating concerning damage and corrosion. Rushton et al. [15] portrayed that off-axis loading of the MAGEC device was leading to asymmetric abrasion, producing the titanium wear debris identified within the internal components and in adjacent soft

tissues. The extending bar has also been identified as a component prone to reoccurring failure, as Joyce identified 100% of retrieved samples to display wear marks on the exterior of the extending bar (Fig 2b). Of the 34 MAGEC devices examined in Joyce's study there was a mean extending bar diameter reduction of 0.22mm, with one component showing a diameter reduction of 1.07mm (17% of original size). Similarly, Panagiotopoulou [14] discovered 100% of assessed extending bars demonstrated evidence of surface degradation. In the existing literature, another component that has been consistently highlighted as a concerning point of failure is the drive-pin. Joyce et al. [16] performed an analysis of explanted MAGEC devices to quantify the rate of drive-pin failures. This study concluded that 50.7% of the 134 devices examined showed evidence of drive-pin fracturing (Fig 2c). Teoh et al. similarly carried out a study which reported evidence of one patient requiring device removal due to fracture of the drive-pin. These reoccurring reports of drive-pin fractures provide evidence that there is an acting load from the spine which is causing this failure mode. Although this information offers valuable insights into the types of failures experienced by the components, the specific loading conditions responsible for these failures have not yet been explored. This study is designed to delve into the stress propagation and values of MAGEC device components when subjected to both compressive and shear loading conditions, utilising Finite Element Analysis (FEA). Through this investigation of the loading conditions that contribute to failure modes, this study aims to acquire knowledge that can inform future EOS treatment techniques and guide design modifications to proactively prevent the recurrence of these issues. This study aims to provide valuable insights into the obstacles faced by the MAGEC device, ultimately improving the reliability and longevity of these critical medical devices. By comprehending the effect of loading conditions on the mechanical behaviour of these implants, significant progress can be made towards enhancing patient outcomes and ensuring the long-term success of spinal interventions.

FIGURE 2 (a) Failed radial bearing, (b) wear marks on the exterior of the extending bar, (c) fractured drive-pin. Reproduced with permissions from [13]

METHODOLOGY

Figure 3a shows an example of an explanted MAGEC growing rod, which was obtained for this study. The dimensions of each component were measured using a digital micrometre and used to construct a 3D model of the MAGEC device using Solidworks 2023 software (Fig 3b).

FIGURE 3 (a) MAGEC device, (b) cross-section view of MAGEC growing rod. From left to right: Extending bar (black); seal housing (orange) with seal (purple); main actuator outer casing (green); lead screw (red); thrust bearing (pink); drive pin (white vertical line); magnet (light blue); radial bearing (white); and coned bar (black). Note that the small, light blue triangles indicate machine welded bands between the different sections of the MAGEC rod [17]

The 3D model file was then imported into ABAQUS 2020 software for Finite Element Analysis (FEA). An elastic material model was employed to simulate how each component of the MAGEC device reacts under compressive and shear loads. The material properties of each component were allocated in ABAQUS as reported in Table 1 (Welsch [18]). All the components except the drive-pin are manufactured using Ti-6Al-4V, which is currently the most popular material used in biomedical spinal implants (Song [19]). The drive-pin and bearing components are manufactured using stainless steel custom grade 465, which is specifically designed for small-diameter applications that require high strength and corrosion resistance (Raposo [20]). Stainless steel 440C was previously used for these applications but has not been used since 2015, and for this reason grade 465 has been employed for this study.

TABLE 1 Material properties of Ti-6Al-4V and custom 465 stainless steel [18], [21]

Material	Young's modulus (E) (GPa)	Poisson's ratio (ν)	Density (ρ) (g/cm ³)	Yield strength (MPa)	Compressive Yield strength (MPa)	Shear strength (MPa)
465 Steel	190	0.28	7.86	1560	1560	900
Ti-6Al-4V	114	0.33	4.41	880	970	550

Each component of the MAGEC's assembly was put through a preliminary mesh convergence study to determine the optimum mesh size. Quadratic tetrahedral, hexahedral, and quadratic element types were employed to suit the geometry of each component and ensure the mesh structure is consistent and of high quality (Fig 4a). The MAGEC device was assembled in ABAQUS in accordance with the device samples examined prior to the FEA model development. Tie constraints were applied to

the coned bar, thrust bearing, magnet, and radial bearing as these components are magnetically connected to avoid any relative movement. Following observation of the structural arrangement after implantation, boundary conditions were applied to both ends of the rod (Fig 4b). BC-1 is fixed in all directions on the coned-bar, whereas BC-2 is fixed in the y and x directions for compression loading and fixed in the x and z directions for shear loading (Fig 4b). The location to which the load is applied is also demonstrated in Figure 4, with the load being distributed over the surface of the extending bar face for both compression and shear loading analysis.

FIGURE 4 (a) FEA mesh of thrust bearing, magnet, and drive-pin (left to right), (b) FEA boundary conditions and load location

It was important to understand how the MAGEC device is surgically implanted and the how the connecting components are interlinked. This research allows the FEA model to be designed in

comparison to the real-life scenario and influence accurate results. Figure 1b demonstrates the MAGEC device is connected to pedicle screws which are drilled into the patient’s spine, ensuring the device remains secure [13]. The vast selection of x-ray images from current literature demonstrates that the quantity of pedicle screws varies depending on patients, meaning each case is unique to the patient’s weight and severity of patient’s spinal deformation angle. All structures however following the system of being fixed from both ends of the device, and this principle will be applied to the boundary conditions of the FEA model. The loads which the device will encounter is also important in ensuring the FEA model is accurate. Implementing the conditions of the scoliosis spinal structure proves difficult due to its complexity, and contrast from the human spine (Raposo [20]). Rohlmann et al. [22] performed a study which analysed the human spine when carrying out various activities, understanding which activities cause high spinal loads to avoid implant failure following surgery. This was achieved by using a modern in vivo measuring instrumented implant, telemetered vertebral body replacement (VBR). Iyer et al. [23] also conducted a study by developing a quasi-static stiffness-based biomechanical model to calculate loads on the thoracic and lumbar spine during bending or lifting tasks. These studies were derived for this FEA model to ensure the magnitude of force is accurate, however due to these studies being adult patient focused, they were adapted to suit the weight of an EOS patient. Hill et al. [24] conducted microscopic imaging analysis on forty dual-rod constructs, retrieved from 36 EOS patients across four medical centres. This study documented the heaviest patient as 40.9 kg, therefore this is the weight selected to transfer Rohlmann and Iyer’s data as this will present the worst-case scenario results. The adaptation of these results was achieved by calculating the ratio between the forces acting on the patients against the body weight recorded. This fraction of the results can then be multiplied by the EOS patient weight identified (40.9kg), and the highest force identified will be applied to the FEA model to test the worst-case scenario. Iyer’s study was adapted by identifying the highest compressive load which was calculated in the thoracic and lumbar spinal sections and using the average of these loads (1622N) against the highest patient weight (104.2kg) as the worst-case scenario (Table 2).

TABLE 2 Loads applied to FEA model [22], [23]

Load	Patient Weight						Load selected for FEA
	66kg	74kg	64kg	60kg	63kg	104.2kg	
Compression	-	-	-	-	-	637N	637 N
Shear	94N	144.5N	16.8N	58N	81.4N	-	144.5 N

RESULTS

After completing compression and shear loading testing, each individual component was analysed to determine its Maximum von Mises' stress (Fig 5). These stress levels were subsequently compared to the yield strength of the respective component to ascertain whether it had experienced mechanical failure. The maximum principal stress was also compared against the compression yield stress of the material from the compression testing results (Fig 7), and the shear stress compared with the shear strength of the material from the shear load test (Fig 6). The stress propagation of the components was also analysed between the loading conditions, identifying how the variation in load type affects

the stress generated. Figure 5 includes a line which visually represents the yield strength of custom 465 stainless steel (1560 MPa) and Ti-6Al-4V (880 MPa). Following the comparison of the FEA results and materials yield strength, it was concluded that the Maximum von Mises' stress didn't exceed the yield strength in any of the components.

FIGURE 5 FEA Maximum von Mises' Stress compression and shear load component results

Figure 6 illustrates the maximum shear stress produces from each component throughout shear loading testing and compares this with the shear strength of the component. This comparison concluded with both the extending bar and radial bearing exceeding the materials shear strength, deeming them as mechanically failed components. Finally, Figure 7 demonstartes the maximum principal stress generated from each component throughout compression loading testing and compares this with the compressive yield strength of the material. This concluded with the drive-pin being the only component which generated a higher maximum stress than the materials yield strength.

FIGURE 6 FEA maximum shear loading stress component results

FIGURE 7 FEA maximum principal stress compression loading component results

One of the components that produced the most significant stress values in the FEA shear load simulations was the radial bearing, which has been previously identified as a recurring failure point in existing literature. In Figure 8a, the radial bearing is depicted during the shear loading test, highlighting the stress concentrated around the outer ring, where the component magnetically connects to the magnet/coned bar. In Figure 8b, we observe the radial bearing after compression loading. Similar to the shear load test, stress is distributed on the outer surface of the component. However, in the case of the compression load, stress is generated within the inner section of the ring. Another component which is of concern from the shear loading results is the extending bar, as the highest stress from the component exceeds the shear strength of the material. However, although the maximum principal stress didn't exceed the compressive yield strength of the material, the stress propagation identified was interesting. Figure 9 illustrates that the high-stress points are highly concentrated at the location where the extending bar and the main actuator's outer casing come into contact. Figure 10 illustrates the stress propagation produced by the drive-pin for both compression and shear loading tests, with both concentrated maximum stress points being identified from both loading types.

FIGURE 8 (a) FEA radial bearing shear test results, (b) FEA radial bearing compression results with bearing balls isolated

FIGURE 9 FEA extending bar compression test results

FIGURE 10 (a) FEA drive-pin compression load test results, (b) FEA drive-pin shear load test results

DISCUSSION

This study marked the first FEA of the MAGEC growing rods performance under compression and shear loading conditions. The results from both loading conditions exhibited similarities to the retrieval observation studies previously discussed. Joyce [13] and Panagiotopoulou *et al* [14] carried out retrieval analysis studies both identifying evidence of failed radial bearings, with Joyce concluding with 74% component failure. Figure 6 illustrates that the Maximum principal stress identified from the radial bearing in shear loading testing exceeds the shear strength of custom 465 stainless steel, deeming the component to have failed mechanically. Joyce's [13] analysis of the failed radial bearing revealed that the inner cage of the component had protruded from the exterior (Fig 2a), and subsequent FEA compression analysis identified elevated stress values within the component's inner cage (Fig 8b). In contrast, during the shear test (Fig 8a), there was no indication of stress in this area. These results imply a correlation, indicating that the compressive load exerted on the spine may be the primary factor contributing to this failure mechanism. The extending bar which displayed 100% evidence of exterior wear marks in both Joyce's and Panagiotopoulou's studies, exhibited Maximum von Mises stress values lower than the yield strength of Ti-6Al-4V. However, the stress propagation between the loading conditions differs significantly. High-stress points are consistently situated on the exterior of the extending bar throughout compression analysis, as depicted in Figure 9. This finding aligns with the observations made by both Joyce and Panagiotopoulou, who identified evidence of wear marks in the same area (Fig 2b). In the shear analysis, high-stress points are localised at the end of the component with stress transferring to the exterior base of the component under changing loading conditions. Finally, when comparing the maximum principal stress of the drive-pin, this component exceeded the compressive yield strength of custom 465 stainless steel, and the stress propagation demonstrated similarities to current literature. Figure 10a-b shows the high stress is in a concentrated point of the drive-pin exterior in both compression and shear loading conditions. The concentrated stress points suggest that a fracture point is possible, and the location which the stress is located draws comparisons to the drive-pin fractures Joyce [13] identified. The importance of understanding the loading conditions which the device encounters and how they affect each component is vital in implementing future adjustments to minimise these potential obstacles. This study has expanded the understanding of the device's mechanical response to different loadings conditions, and provided valuable insight which can be adopted for future improvements and developments in this field.

CONCLUSION

This study has delved into the intricate realm of the MAGEC device, aiming to decipher the mechanical behaviour through FEA under varying loading conditions. Notably, these findings indicate that the compressive load applied to the spine emerges as a significant factor in the observed failure mechanisms. The examination of compression and shear loading tests has shown distinct stress distribution patterns, shedding light on the nuanced response of these implants to different loading scenarios. Furthermore, this research aligns with existing literature, documenting the evidence of wear marks on the extending bar, which consistently exhibited stress concentration. These observations further emphasise the need for careful consideration and refinement in the design and application of magnetically expanding spinal implants. As the field of spinal implant technology continues to evolve, this study contributes valuable data to the ongoing pursuit of safer and more effective solutions for spinal treatments. Regarding future work in this field, FEA should continue to be utilised when mechanically analysing medical implants. FEA can be extended to dynamic scenarios in which the implant is simulated under various physiological movements to better understand performance in real life scenarios. Due to the complexity of the EOS spine, it is difficult to replicate the conditions which the device will be encountering, and this may be a beneficial step towards increasing simulation accuracy.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

EOS – Early onset scoliosis

FEA – Finite element analysis

MAGEC - Magnetic Expansion Control

REFERENCE LIST

- (1) Hresko, M.T., *NEJOM*, Vol. 368, No. 9, 2013, pp. 834-841.
- (2) Ágústsson, A., Sveinsson, T., Pope, P. and Rodby-Bousquet., *DAR*, Vol. 41, No. 26, 2019, pp. 3198-3202.
- (3) Karol, L.A., *JOPO*, No. 39, 2019, pp. S38-S43
- (4) Teoh, K.H., et al., *TSJ*, Vol. 16, No. 4, 2016, pp. S34-S39.
- (5) Dede, O., and Sturm, P.F., *JOCO*, Vol. 5, No. 10, 2016, pp. 405-411.
- (6) Anari, J.B., et al., *SD*, No. 8, 2020, pp. 295-302.
- (7) Fletcher, N.D., and Bruce, R.W., *CRIMM*, Vol. 5, 2012, pp. 102-110.
- (8) Bess, S., et al., *JBJS*, Vol. 15, No. 92, 2010, pp. 2533-2543.
- (9) Jenks, M., et al., *AHEAHP*, No. 12, 2014, pp. 587-599.

- (10) Hickey, B.A., et al., *ESJ*, Vol. 23, 2014, pp. 61-65.
- (11) Heydar, A.M., Sirazi, S. and Bezer, M., *S*, Vol. 41, No. 22, 2016, pp. E1336-E1342.
- (12) Dannawi, Z., et al., *TB&JJ*, Vol. 95, No. 1, 2013, pp.75-80.
- (13) Joyce, T.J., et al., *S*, Vol. 43, No. 1, 2018, pp. E16-E22.
- (14) Panagiotopoulou, V.C., et al., *ESJ*, Vol. 26, 2017, pp.1699-1710.
- (15) Rushton, P.R.P., et al., *S*, Vol. 44, 2019, pp. 233–239.
- (16) Joyce, T.J., et al., *S*, Vol. 45, No. 13, 2020, pp. 872-876.
- (17) Jones, C.S., et al., *JOOCR*, Vol. 11, No. 8, 2021, pp. 6.
- (18) Welsch, G., Boyer, R. and Collings, E.W., *ASMI*, 1993.
- (19) Song, C.H., et al., *AS*, Vol. 11, No. 17, 2021, pp. 8023.
- (20) Raposo, H., *AM&P*, Vol. 167, No. 9, 2009, pp. 23-25.
- (21) An, G., Liu, R.J. and Yin, G.Q., *M*, Vol. 13, No. 1, 2020, pp. 238.
- (22) Rohlmann, A., et al., *PO*, Vol. 9, Vol. 5, 2014, pp. e98510
- (23) Iyer, S., et al., *CB*, Vol. 25, No. 9, 2010, pp. 853-858.
- (24) Hill, G., et al., *TSJ*, Vol. 17, No. 10, 2017, pp. 1506-1518.